

Translation of Situation Awareness Rating Technique Questionnaire in Slovenian

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Abstract

The Situational Awareness Rating Technique (SART) is a questionnaire designed to assess situational awareness when operating a machine. It consists of ten questions corresponding to ten dimensions that can be used to assess an operator's situational awareness when interacting with and operating a machine. Although initially developed for assessment situational awareness of pilots, with the rising complexity of vehicles and introduction of automation, its use has spread significantly in automotive domain in the past decade. In this paper, we present the Slovenian version of the original questionnaire and the process of its development. For the translation of the questionnaire SART into Slovenian, the standard procedures for the translation of research instruments were applied: translation, coordination, back-translation into the source language, comparison of the back-translation with the source text and final coordination. Lastly, it was validated against a reference system in a driving-based environment.

Keywords

Situational awareness rating technique, situational awareness, in-vehicle human-machine interaction, questionnaire, translation

1. Introduction

Situational awareness (SA) or knowing what is going on around you is essential in any dynamic human decision-making process because it provides the level of knowledge needed to make informed decisions and take appropriate actions [1]. There is not a single agreed upon definition of situational awareness, but the three most commonly used definitions (see **Table 1**) all seem to refer to three aspects that constitute a situationally aware operator: gathering information from the environment to obtain a knowledge of the situation, interpreting the perceived information to understand its meaning in relation to the observed system, and being able to plan or project the next step of the system's operation.

All these aspects indicate that SA is a cognitive construct that requires multiple resources rather than a single one. As such, SA is also inextricably linked to other cognitive theories, such as attention, short term and long-term memory, and cognitive workload. Cognitive workload is often defined as a function of the supply and demand of attentional and processing resources [2].

It is constrained by the operator's limited short-term memory (working memory), and processing resources are influenced by the operator's domain knowledge in long-term memory [3]. More experienced operators have a broader range of skills and can therefore process larger or more complex information in their working memory. At the same time, as the workload increases, more attention is required for task performance, leaving fewer resources for situational awareness [2]. In this regard, SA competes with task performance for attentional and processing resources. Assessing situational awareness is therefore not an easy task and requires the observation of several psychological constructs.

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Table 1
Definitions of situational awareness

Author	SA definition
Endsley, 1988. [4]	“Situational awareness is the perception of the elements in the environment within a volume of time and space, the comprehension of their meaning and a projection of their status in the near future.”
Smith & Hancock, 1995. [5]	“Situational awareness is the invariant in the agent-environment system that generates the momentary knowledge and behavior required to attain the goals specified by an arbiter of performance in the environment.”
Bedny & Meister, 1999. [6]	“Situational awareness is the conscious dynamic reflection on the situation by an individual. It provides dynamic orientation to the situation, the opportunity to reflect not only the past, present and future, but the potential features of the situation. The dynamic reflection contains logical-conceptual, imaginative, conscious and unconscious components which enables individuals to develop mental models of external events.”

Although there is more than one theory, the most popular theory of situational awareness proposes a three level SA model (**Figure 1**), which suggests that achieving SA requires perceiving the elements of the environment (level 1), understanding on their meaning (level 2), and being able to project their status in the near future (level 3) [2]. Based on this model, numerous assessment procedures have been developed that aim to capture all aspects of SA.

Figure 1: Situational awareness model [7].

The three broad groups into which they can be classified are self-assessment, inferential and query procedures. Self-assessment procedures, usually based on questionnaires and scales, survey participants' self-perceptions to look for subjective signs of SA. Inference-based techniques look for implicit clues about the presence or absence of SA in the context of an individual's performance and behavior. Finally, query techniques look for direct evidence of the

content of SA. This approach provides a set of information about the person's perception and understanding of the situation, which is then compared to an established ground truth.

The first and still most widely used query method for assessing SA is the Situation Awareness Global Assessment Technique or SAGAT [8],[9]. SAGAT was originally used to assess SA of industrial machinery operators, but was later used and adapted for numerous other domains. The operator is presented with a simulation of a device they are supposed to operate. Using a frame-freeze technique, the simulation is paused at random critical situations and the operator is asked various machine- and environment-related questions to determine his or her SA at that moment. The operator's answers are then compared to predefined correct answers that attempt to cover all three levels of SA. Since stopping the process for each query can significantly affect the operator's behavior and responses, the frame-freeze query method does not allow realistic observation of a process in its natural environment. As a more suitable alternative to the query-based approach, a real-time-based method have been proposed, such as the Situation Present Assessment Method (SPAM) [10]. SPAM distinguishes the workload from SA by alerting the operator that a question (similar to the ones used in SAGAT) is waiting while they are actually operating the machine. The time to accept the question, the time to answer the question, and the error rate are then evaluated as indicators of SA.

Because of its simplicity and cost-effectiveness, another common method of assessing SA that does not affect the operation of the machine, is self-assessment through the use of questionnaires after a task has been completed. One of the most popular and widely used methods is the Situational Awareness Rating Technique or SART [11],[12], which was originally developed to assess the situational awareness of pilots. However, it has also been used to assess situational awareness of operators in a variety of other domains, as the dimensions of SART are general in nature, and attempt to provide an insight into the three most important domains of SA: attentional demand, attentional supply and understanding of the perceived information.

1.1. Situational Awareness in Vehicles

SA has been recognized as an important factor in the automotive domain as it provides important information on driver behavior, and is helpful in the process of design and evaluation of advanced driver assistance systems (ADAS). Driving as a task can be especially demanding as it consists of more tasks that run concurrently (maintain longitudinal and lateral control, follow traffic rules, adapt to other traffic participants, adapt to weather and road conditions, etc.). With increased automation some of these tasks are controlled by the vehicle, which makes the driving task easier, but at the same time, in moments when the driver has to take over control of the vehicle, makes regain of SA much harder. Some of the ADASs such as parking sensors, back rear camera and blind spot sensor systems were indeed introduced to increase driver's SA. A lot of other ADAS for obtaining longitudinal (adaptive cruise control) and lateral control (lane keep assist) on the other hand, assist the performance of the driving task in terms of safety and comfort by reducing the driver's control of the vehicle. This opens space for performance of non-driving related tasks, which can make the driving process more entertaining and less demanding, however it can also negatively affect driving safety.

Increase of ADASs in vehicles thus reveals the need to identify potential negative side effects as of any new technology introduced to the vehicle and implement better human-machine interaction (HMI) models to exploit their benefits while eliminating (or at least reducing) negative influences on driving safety. Using methods such as SART can contribute to this understanding.

2. Situational Awareness Rating Technique (SART)

SART is a questionnaire-based technique consisting of ten questions that ask the operator about different dimensions of situational awareness: instability, complexity and variability of situation, arousal, spare mental capacity, concentration and division of attention, information quantity and

quality, and familiarity with the situation. The operator answers the questions on a seven-point rating scale, where 1 = Low and 7 = High, to indicate their assessment rating of the situation about the specific dimension. The ten questions correspond to ten dimensions of SA, which are then grouped into the three SA constructs: attentional demand, attentional supply and understanding of the situation as presented in **Table 2**. After the trial, participants are asked to rate each dimension on a seven-point Likert scale (1 being the lowest and 7 being the highest) according to how well they performed on the task analyzed. The ratings are then combined to calculate a measure of the participant's situational dimension using the formula $SA = U - (D - S)$, where U is the summed Understanding, D is the summed attentional Demand, and S is the summed attentional Supply. From the formula, it is easy to see that the questionnaire suggests that there is a negative effect on understanding and an overall reduction of SA when demand exceeds supply.

The SART approach is also available in a faster version known as 3D SART. The 3D SART uses a 100-point scale from 0 (low) to 100 (high), for each measure (demand for attentional resources, supply of attentional resources and understanding of the situation). The overall SART score is then calculated similarly to the original scale, i.e. $SA = U - (D - S)$, where U is the score for understanding, D is the score for attentional demand and S is the score for attentional supply.

Table 2
SART dimensions [12]

Domain	Dimension	Definition
Attentional demand	Instability of the situation	Likelihood of situation to change suddenly
	Complexity of the situation	Degree of complication of situation
	Variability of the situation	Number of variables that require attention
Attentional supply	Arousal	Degree that one is ready for activity
	Spare mental capacity	Amount of mental ability available for new variables
	Concentration of attention	Degree that thoughts are brought to bear on the situation
	Division of attention	Amount of division of attention in the situation
Understanding	Information quantity	Amount of knowledge received and understood
	Information quality	Degree of goodness of value of knowledge communicated
	Familiarity with situation	Degree of acquaintance with situation experience

2.1. Motivation for This Paper

Standardized questionnaires for assessing SA are an important tool for performing SA research as they provide methods that allow direct comparison of research results conducted in different settings. However, because these methods are only available in English, they can be used by native English speakers or those fluent in English. The latter are still exposed to potential cultural differences that may affect their comprehension, which may reduce the reliability and validity of the methods. Therefore, the main motivation for conducting this research was to expand the applicability of this method also to non-native English speakers, and to help SA researchers

collect data also with non-English speaking communities and users, which can lead to assessment of SA in new domains and areas. To our best knowledge a Slovenian translation of any SA standardized questionnaire does not exist. While there are reports on the use of SART in Slovenia [13], there are no reports on the translation process nor is the translation publicly available. Looking at the available research on SA, we find that in addition to Slovenia, SART has been used for assessment of SA in several non-English speaking countries, such as Portugal [14], Germany [15][16], Sweden [17], Norway [18], Korea [19][20] and China [21]. However, the authors rarely report in which language SART was presented to the study' participants (e.g., [15], [16], [19] and [21]), or if translated, which method was used (e.g., [14] or [18]). An exception is a Korean translation, where the authors used back-translation and expert knowledge to obtain a validated Korean SART – (K-SART) [20]. If the questionnaires are not in the native language of the respondents, this may affect the respondents' comprehension of what they are assessing, and consequently, affect their responses, calling into question the reliability of the results obtained. This problem is exacerbated when standardized methods are used as reference systems when evaluating new methods for assessing SA, as was the case with Satuf et al. [14] and Parka et al. [19]. This is primarily because the benefits of a validated standardized method are lost if not used in the manner in which the method was validated. This makes the interpretation of such results less reliable and raises questions about the actual sensitivity of the newly proposed methods.

3. Methodology

3.1. User study

For the translation of the questionnaire SART into Slovenian, the standard procedures for the translation of research instruments (translation, coordination, back-translation into the source language, comparison of the back-translation with the source text, final coordination) were applied [22].

The English version of the SART questionnaire was independently translated into Slovenian by three translators who are native Slovenian speakers. Two of them were professional translators who were not familiar with the concepts that the questionnaire was intended to measure, and the third translator was an expert in the field and fluent in English. According to the recommendations of Tsang et al. [23], it is important that at least one of the translators is familiar with the concepts that the questionnaire is intended to measure in order to produce a translation that is closer to the original instrument. In this way, subtle differences in the original questionnaire could be identified and corrected by the expert group. The independent forward translations were combined into one document along with the original questions in English. The order of the proposed translations was randomized to exclude possible bias toward a particular translator.

An expert panel was then organized to discuss the proposed translations. Seven experts (native Slovenian speakers with at least B2 English proficiency level) from the fields of human-computer interaction, cognition, philosophy, transportation and driving safety were invited to serve on the panel. Three of the participants were from the University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, one from Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts, two from the University of Maribor, Faculty of Logistics and one was from the Slovenian Traffic Safety Agency.

The panelists discussed the translation of each questionnaire item, considering idiomatic, semantic, conceptual, and terminological aspects, until consensus was reached on a single translation that was acceptable to all panelists. In some cases, the panelists selected one of the three proposed translations without making any changes, but in other cases, they combined parts of two proposed translations to produce the final translation (see **Figure 2**). The panelists then proceeded to the next item on the questionnaire.

Once the Slovenian translation of the questionnaire was agreed upon, three other professional translators (who were not related to those who had translated the questionnaire into Slovenian) were hired to translate the accepted translations back into English to ensure that the meaning

was preserved. The translators had not previously seen the original English text of the questionnaires and were not familiar with the concepts the questionnaire was intended to measure, as recommended by Tsang et al. [23].

Original: Arousal

How aroused are you in the situation? Are you alert and ready for activity (High) or do you have a low degree of alertness (Low)?

Translation 1: Vznemirjenost

Kako vas situacija vznemirja? Ste vedno budni in pripravljeni delovati (Visoko) ali je vaša raven budnosti nizka (Nizko)?

Translation 2: Vznemirjenost

Kako vznemirjeni ste v tej situaciji? Ali ste budni in pripravljeni na aktivnost (visoka stopnja) ali pa je vaša budnost nizka (nizka stopnja)?

Translation 3: Vzburjenost

Kako vzburjeni ste v tej situaciji? Ste zbrani in pripravljeni na dejanja (Visoka) ali je vaša zbranost nizka (Nizka)?

The agreed upon translation: Vzburjenost

Kako vzburjeni ste v tej situaciji? Ste zbrani in pripravljeni na aktivnost (Visoka) ali je vaša zbranost nizka (Nizka)?

Figure 2: An example of the accepted translation, which consists of a combination of parts of the two proposed translations.

Finally, the working group compared the two English texts and, where necessary, formulated a more appropriate Slovenian form. All final forms of the translation, named SI-SART for simplicity, were adopted with the agreement of all members of the working group and are presented in **Table 3**.

4. Questionnaire validation

The concurrent validity of the questionnaire was evaluated with a short user study. As a reference method, the Situation Present Assessment Method (SPAM) was used. The study was conducted in a simulated driving environment in which the operator (driver) operated a vehicle.

Table 3

Original SART and translated SART in Slovenian – SI-SART

SART	SI-SART
Title Situation awareness rating technique	Naslov Metoda ocenjevanja situacijskega zavedanja
Instability of situation How changeable is the situation? Is the situation highly unstable and likely to change suddenly (High) or is it very stable and straightforward (Low)?	Nestabilnost situacije Kako spremenljiva je situacija? Ali je situacija zelo nestabilna in se lahko nenadoma spremeni (Visoka) ali pa je zelo stabilna in jasna (Nizka)?
Complexity of the situation How complicated is the situation? Is it complex with many interrelated components (High) or is it simple and straightforward (Low)?	Kompleksnost situacije Kako zapletena je situacija? Je situacija kompleksna z mnogimi medsebojno povezanimi elementi (Visoka) ali je enostavna in jasna (Nizka)?
Variability of the situation How many variables are changing within the situation? Are there a large number of factors varying (High) or are there very few variables changing?	Spremenljivost situacije Koliko dejavnikov se spreminja v okviru situacije? Se spreminja veliko število dejavnikov (Visoka) ali se spreminja zelo malo spremenljivk (Nizka)?
Arousal How aroused are you in the situation? Are you alert and ready for activity (High) or do you have a low degree of alertness (Low)?	Vzbujenost Kako vzburjeni ste v tej situaciji? Ste zbrani in pripravljeni na aktivnost (Visoka) ali je vaša zbranost nizka (Nizka)?
Concentration of Attention How much are you concentrating on the situation? Are you concentrating on many aspects of the situation (High) or focused on only one (Low)?	Koncentracija pozornosti V kolikšni meri ste osredotočeni na situacijo? Se osredotočate na več vidikov situacije (Visoka) ali le na enega (Nizka)?
Division of Attention How much is your attention divided in the situation? Are you concentrating on many aspects of the situation (High) or focused on only one (Low)?	Delitev pozornosti V kolikšni meri je vaša pozornost v tej situaciji razdeljena? Ste osredotočeni na več vidikov situacije (Visoko) ali le na enega (Nizko)?
Spare Mental Capacity How much mental capacity do you have to spare in the situation? Do you have sufficient to attend to many variables (High) or nothing to spare at all (Low)?	Prosta umska zmogljivost Kolikšna je vaša še razpoložljiva umska zmogljivost v tej situaciji? Je imate dovolj, da lahko spremljate več dejavnikov (Visoka), ali je sploh nimate na razpolago (Nizka)?
Information Quantity How much information have you gained about the situation? Have you received and understood a great deal of knowledge (High) or very little (Low)?	Količina informacij Koliko informacij o situaciji ste pridobili? Ste prejeli veliko informacij in jih razumeli (Visoka) ali zelo malo (Nizka)?
Familiarity with Situation How familiar are you with the situation? Do you have a great deal of relevant experience (High) or is it a new situation (Low)?	Poznavanje situacije V kolikšni meri že poznate situacijo? Imate veliko relevantnih izkušenj s situacijo (Nizko) ali je situacija za vas nova (Visoko)?

4.1. Situation Present Assessment Method (SPAM)

The Situation Present Assessment Method (SPAM) is a real-time-based method [10] that asks the operator questions about their situational awareness while operating a machine. The time to accept the question (request response time), the time to answer the question (answer response time), and the success and error rate are then evaluated as indicators of SA. By providing the option for the operator to choose when to accept a new question request, this method allows for safer and less (critical) interruptions of the completing their primary task (operating a machine). However, this introduces a new factor that has to be considered when analyzing the results on time to answer question. The operator might take the time to accept the request to gain understanding of the elements of the environment and the current situation the machine is, and only then accept the request. As a consequence, they could respond to the question much quicker compared to operators that would accept the request when seeing it, without prior situational assessment of the environment. Both of these factors further impact the success rate of the queries, highlighting the need to observe all three factors when using this method.

For this study, the SPAM method was implemented in the form of a mobile application displayed on a head-down display mounted on the physical dashboard in the driving simulator. It was placed to the right of the steering wheel within reach of the driver so that he or she could easily accept and answer SPAM queries. Ten questions were used in the study to assess the driver's situational awareness, all related to driving and operating the vehicle. As defined by SPAM, the application would first prompt a question request, which the driver could either accept or decline. If accepted, the driver was presented with a question with four possible answers, only one of which was correct. There was also always an "I do not know" option. Two examples are presented in **Figure 3**.

What is the current speed limit?	What was the last road sign for?
a) 30 km/h	a) Speed limit
b) 50 km/h	b) Yield
c) 60 km/h	c) Stop sign
d) I do not know	d) I do not know

Figure 3: Example of questions presented with the SPAM method to assess driver's situational awareness.

To avoid anticipation effects, the question requests were presented in random intervals between 60 to 120 seconds. In the case of a declined question request, a new prompt would appear at a random interval of 20 to 30 seconds.

The question request time, the time to answer, and the number of correct answers were recorded and used as reference measures for validating SART.

4.2. Study design

13 participants took part in the study. The participants first and primary task was safe driving. The participants' secondary, but equally important, task was to answer to SPAM questions. They were instructed to try to complete the SPAM tasks as quickly and as accurately as possible, without neglecting the operation of the vehicle or engaging in any dangerous driving behavior.

After the drive, the participants were asked to complete the SART questionnaire.

4.3. Study results

Table 4 shows the situational awareness results obtained with SI-SART, while **Table 5** shows the situational awareness results obtained with SPAM. A correlation test was used to test for correlations between the two sets of results; the calculated Pearson correlation is $r(13) = 0.49, p$

= 0.087, 95% CI [-.08, .82], please see **Figure 4**. Although this result did not reach conventional significance, the correlation exceeds the typical validity threshold of .30, providing evidence for the concurrent validity of the Slovene translation. The wide confidence interval reflects the small sample size, suggesting that further validation with a larger cohort is needed.

Table 4
SPAM results

Participant ID	Request response time [ms]	Answer response time [ms]	Correct answers [%]
1	M=3553.7, SD=4675.2	M=13140.7, SD=11472.6	80
2	M=7616.0, SD=10230.0	M=21569.8, SD=11472.4	70
3	M=3185.9, SD=614.2	M=11383.8, SD=5980.9	90
4	M=5807.4, SD=11138.1	M=10523.6, SD=4838.7	80
5	M=8007.3, SD=15917.1	M=14512.1, SD=6579.7	70
6	M=3329.1, SD=725.6	M=10104.0, SD=4823.7	60
7	M=8335.6, SD=10754.8	M=33395.1, SD=21166.5	80
8	M=3275.1, SD=2429.2	M=12315.5, SD=5247.3	90
9	M=2389.5, SD=594.9	M=8599.8, SD=3269.6	90
10	M=2672.0, SD=1473.3	M=10955.6, SD=5985.6	70
11	M=7805.4, SD=3816.0	M=13440.0, SD=5561.8	90
12	M=2910.8, SD=2294.0	M=12878.9, SD=7674.7	100
13	M=6212.9, SD=5903.2	M=8838.8, SD=3685.2	60

Table 5
SI-SART results

Participant ID	SART-U	SART-D	SART-S	Overall score U-(D-S)
1	-1	-6	10	15
2	2	2	6	6
3	5	-7	10	22
4	-1	-5	4	8
5	5	-6	10	21
6	1	-4	9	14
7	2	3	4	3
8	4	-2	11	17
9	0	-2	7	9
10	2	0	3	5
11	4	2	8	10
12	5	-6	11	22
13	0	0	3	3

5. Discussion

The main goal of this research was to translate the SART questionnaire for assessing SA to enable its use for Slovenian speakers. The multi-step translation process included all of the steps required for the translation of the questionnaire – initial translation, coordination, back translation into the source language, comparison of the back translation with the source text, and final coordination. The translated version SART was also evaluated with the SPAM method, further confirming the adequacy of SI-SART.

SART can be used in multiple domains, but in this specific case we focused on the automotive domain for validation of the translated questionnaire. By involving multiple expert profiles

(linguistics, human-computer interaction, cognition, philosophy, transportation and driving safety) in the translation process, a holistic approach was taken that although primarily focusing on driving, it still attempted to retain the possibility of using SI-SART in multiple domains, as it was intended for the original SART.

The translated version will enable Slovenian researchers to use the SART questionnaire confidently without worries of losing information due to language or cultural specifics and enrich the scientific community on global scale by enable direct comparisons among research conducted in different countries. Moreover, it will enable researchers around the world to include Slovenian speaking participants in their studies, or use data collected by Slovenian researchers expanding the possibility to share data sets and research information.

Figure 4: SI-SART and SPAM results per participant

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